

Relation Between Power of Probability and Shannon's Entropy with Consequences on Tsallis and Renyi Entropies

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According to Boltzmann, entropy (in the Shannon case) is $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$. This may be written as: $k \ln(1/\text{number of states})$ where $1/\text{number of states}$ then plays the role of a probability. In the case of maximization of entropy subject to an a priori constraint, one does not actually require \ln of probability. The introduction of \ln converts a product $1/\text{Product } i N! / n(e)!$ into a sum, making the math much simpler as is well-known. We point out further that: $\ln(\text{Probability}(e1) + \delta) = \ln(\text{Probability}(e1) + \delta/\text{Probability})$. In other words, in the infinitesimal case, one may see a sum leading to a sum of $\ln(\text{Prob})$ and a term $\delta/\text{probability}$ proportional to the infinitesimal change in probability. (This observation is relevant to Renyi entropy.) Finally, we note that Shannon's entropy may be obtained from $\text{Probability} = \text{product over } i \pi_i \text{ power } N \pi_i \text{ for large } N$. This is equivalent to $\exp\{\sum N \pi_i \ln(\pi_i)\}$. In other words, Shannon's entropy is closely linked to the power of probability.

We mention the above features, because as we have argued in previous notes (1), that powers of probabilities appear in physical situations, i.e. $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$, where q is a real number. In other words, there are two probabilities $f(e_i)$ and $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$. This then begs the question: What should the number of states associated with the unnormalized $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$ be? Instead of considering this question, one may note that for $q=1$, $f(e_i)$ is known to be associated with Shannon's entropy. Now Shannon's entropy is linked with $\ln(\text{number of states})$, but if there is an infinitesimal in the power, one may actually produce a Shannon's entropy term, i.e. $f(e_i) \text{ power } (1+\delta) = \exp(\ln(f) (1+\delta)) \approx f(1+\delta \ln(f))$

The point is that one may start with an expression of a probability to a power and find that it actually yields Shannon's entropy if the power contains an infinitesimal. We argue that this seems to be the strategy behind Tsallis entropy. An expression which, on the surface, seems to represent probabilities may produce Shannon's entropy if one may introduce an infinitesimal into the power, i.e. $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$ for $q \rightarrow 1 + \delta$ where $\delta \rightarrow 0$. In other words, $q=1$ really means $q \rightarrow 1 + \delta$, we , and this reveals the inherent Shannon's entropy associated with $f(e_i)$, we argue.

We also apply these ideas to Renyi entropy.

Tsallis Entropy and the Notion of Probability

Boltzmann introduced entropy as:

$$- k \ln(\text{Number of states}) = k \ln(1/\text{number of states}) = \ln(1/\text{probability}) \quad ((1))$$

His entropy expression is \ln of a probability. Similarly, Renyi entropy is:

$$\ln(\sum \text{over } i \pi_i \text{ power } q) / (q-1) \quad ((2))$$

Again, one sees the notion of \ln and extensivity. Tsallis entropy on the other hand is not extensive and does not contain \ln :

$$\text{Tsallis entropy} = \frac{1}{1-q} \left\{ 1 - \sum_i p_i^q \right\} \quad ((3))$$

In general, it seems that Tsallis entropy is presented as a math function which has the property that for $q=1$, one obtains Shannon's entropy.

The point we wish to make is that p_i^q is an unnormalized probability, not an entropy, so why should Tsallis entropy yield an entropy in the limit $q \rightarrow 1$? We try to argue that this is related to the idea that Shannon's entropy is strongly linked to the notion of a probability to a power. In fact, it formally appears as an argument of an exponential, as we show in the next section, so that if it is multiplied by a δ , then one may expand the exponential as $1 + \delta$ Shannon's entropy.

Shannon's Entropy and its Link to Powers of Probability

Although there are various ways of obtaining Shannon's entropy, we wish to consider a well-known approach in the literature linked to powers of probabilities. The idea is that if one has a set of probabilities p_i (such that $\sum_i p_i = 1$) representing i possible outcomes, then if one tosses a die, so to speak, N times, where $N \gg 1$, then:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Probability for a set of results} &= \frac{1}{\text{Product over } i \text{ } p_i^N} \\ &= \exp - \left\{ \sum_i p_i \ln(p_i) \right\} \quad ((4)) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, Shannon's entropy appears as the power of the exponential and $\ln(\text{probability})$ yields it explicitly. There seems to be a key distinction between probability and entropy as $\ln(\text{probability})$ which is in keeping with Boltzmann's definition:

$$\text{entropy} = -k \ln(\text{number of states}) = k \ln(1/\text{number of states}) = k \ln(\text{probability}) \quad ((5))$$

and even Renyi entropy:

$$\frac{1}{q-1} \ln(\sum_i p_i^q) \quad ((6))$$

((5)) and ((6)) explicitly use the \ln function. We argue, however, that it is not necessary to impose this function, because one may "bring down" Shannon's entropy from the exponential in ((4)) by use of an infinitesimal and not \ln .

In particular, if one has instead of ((4)), the expression:

$$\exp(\delta \left\{ \sum_i p_i \ln(p_i) \right\}) \text{ then this is approx} = 1 + \delta \text{ Shannon's entropy} \quad ((7))$$

The question becomes: How does a δ appear in the first place?

The Notion of a Product of Probabilities

Shannon's entropy $-k \sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ applies to a probability $f(e_i)$. As noted in (1), it is possible to have $f(e_i)$ power q appear in a physical problem, due to cycling/frequency considerations. For example, we considered $f(e_i)$ as the probability that a sunflower seed is not eaten by a bird or mammal in a day. We use the period of a day because it is naturally occurring. Each day, the probability applies independently. In order for the seed to germinate, q days must pass, but as long as the seed is not eaten, it germinates with almost 100% probability. The probability for a sunflower seed to germinate is:

$$f(e_i)^q \quad ((8))$$

Here e_i is the amount of fruit produced by a seed which is considered to also be linked to the probability for the seed to be eaten. For example, a seed might produce very well in a clear region which is sunny and near a stream. This, however, is exactly the same place where one might find many birds and small mammals, rather than in a swampy area which is also not great for fruit production.

Even though ((8)) is the probability relevant to the sunflower seed problem, $f(e_i)$ should be directly associated with Shannon's entropy. If $q=1$, one would simply have a Shannon's entropy situation. We note, however, that $q=1$, $f(e_i)$ is a probability and not an entropy and that ((8)) is also a probability.

The traditional approach of Boltzmann/Shannon entropy is to maximize it subject to an a priori constraint. Such a physical a priori constraint exists for the sunflower seed, namely:

$$\sum_i e_i f(e_i)^q \quad ((9))$$

Now, there is no reason that one needs to maximize $\ln(\text{probability})$ as is done in the Boltzmann/Shannon case. One could just as well maximize/minimize an expression containing probabilities. If that is the case, one could anticipate a function of ((8)), i.e.

$$\text{Function}(f(e_i)^q) \quad ((10))$$

The question becomes: What should ((10)) become when $q=1$? In such a case, one would have:

$$\text{Function}(f(e_i)) \quad ((11))$$

It is already known, however, that $-\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ is a solution for ((11)) in the $q=1$ case if one wishes to have a sum. If ((10)) should contain a sum of $f(e_i)^q$ terms, then in the $q=1$ case, it should reduce to Shannon's entropy. The problem is that $f(e_i)^q$ is a probability, not an entropy, while Shannon's entropy is an entropy and not a probability. The

resolution of this issue is to have a power of a probability yield an entropy if an infinitesimal appears in the power. In other words:

$$f(e_i) \text{ power } q \rightarrow f(e_i) \text{ power } 1+\delta \approx f(e_i) \{1 + \delta \ln(f(e_i))\} \quad ((12))$$

Thus, it is possible to have an AND power of $f(e_i)$ scenario which is a probability sum which yields a Shannon's entropy sum in the following way:

$$\{1 - \text{Sum over } i f(e_i) \text{ power } 1+\delta\} / \delta \quad ((13))$$

Converting back to q , one has Tsallis entropy based on a sum of power probabilities which nevertheless yields a Shannon's entropy expression in the $q=1$ limit:

$$\{1 - \text{Sum over } i f(e_i) \text{ power } q\} / (1-q) \quad ((14))$$

Renyi Entropy

In the above sections, we argued that $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$, even though it is a probability, can give rise to Shannon entropy terms if q contains an infinitesimal δ . We applied this idea to the $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$ terms in Tsallis entropy, but the same $f(e_i) \text{ power } q$ appear in Renyi entropy as well. Renyi entropy, however, already has a \ln term:

$$\text{Renyi entropy} = 1/(q-1) \ln\{ \text{Sum over } i f(e_i) \text{ power } q \} \quad ((15))$$

It is known, however, that $\ln(1+\delta) \approx \delta$ so for $q \rightarrow 1 + \delta$ ((15)) becomes:

$$1/\delta (\delta \text{ Sum over } i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))) \quad ((16))$$

which is proportional to Shannon's entropy.

Thus, a similar argument holds for Renyi entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Tsallis entropy has the appearance of a sum of powers of probabilities $f(e_i)$ and not an entropy, which is associated with \ln of a probability. This is fine because there is no reason why one has to extremize a function which is a \ln of probability. The issue is that in the $q=1$ case ($f(e_i) \text{ power } q$), the function which is to be maximized (and is in the form of a sum) is Shannon's entropy: $-\text{Sum over } i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$. The question then becomes: How does an entropy appear from a sum of probabilities to a power q ? We argue that this does occur if q contains an infinitesimal, i.e. in the case of $q \rightarrow 1$ we argue that this is really $q=1+\delta$ and an exponential $\exp((1+\delta) \ln(f(e_i))$ breaks down to: $f(e_i) (1+\delta \ln(f(e_i)))$. If one has a $-f(e_i)$ and a δ in the denominator, one recovers Shannon's entropy. We suggest that this is the manner in which Tsallis entropy, which contains a sum of probabilities, also restores an entropy in the case of power q which contains an infinitesimal. We show that a similar idea holds for Renyi entropy.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on an Example of Maximiation of Tsallis Entropy Subject to a Constraint Part 2 (preprint, zenodo, 2025)